

STYLISTIC FEATURES OF THE USE OF MODAL CONSTRUCTIONS IN ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES

Salavatova Liliya Enverovna.

Master student of Namangan State Institute of Foreign Languages,
salavatovaliliya8@gmail.com

Keywords: Modality, modal verbs, comparative analysis, unproductive verb, multifunctional verbs, utterance, shade of meaning, semantic side, modal constructions, formal and informal contexts.

Abstract: Stylistic features of the use of modal constructions in linguistics as a manifestation of the speaker's attitude toward the utterance's content is the focus of this article. In addition, modalities serve as a grammatical-semantic category that conveys the speaker's attitude toward the utterance and his evaluation of how closely the speech being reported corresponds to reality. Additionally, the paper addresses and offers solutions for the issues associated with translating modal constructions.

Introduction.

The stylistic analysis of modality in English and Russian reveals key insights into how each language uses modality to shape tone, manage formality, and meet cultural expectations. In English, modality often serves as a flexible tool that enables speakers and writers to convey a range of attitudes from politeness to authority, reflecting the language's emphasis on individuality and non-intrusiveness. English modality's reliance on a standardized set of modal verbs across contexts supports an adaptable approach to communication, where modality can be softened or strengthened based on the speaker's intent. Russian, by contrast, employs modality through a combination of direct modal particles, verbs, and context-specific structures, resulting in a pragmatic approach that emphasizes clarity, sincerity, and relational closeness. Russian modality often appears more straightforward and assertive, which reflects cultural norms that prioritize transparency and social bonds.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In both English and Russian, modality serves not only as a grammatical tool but also as a stylistic device that shapes the tone, formality, and stylistic characteristics of discourse. English modality, with its reliance on a distinct set of modal verbs, offers flexibility in creating nuanced tones that can adapt to both formal and informal contexts. By choosing specific modal verbs, English speakers and writers can convey a range of attitudes—from polite suggestion to strong assertion—enabling them to modulate their tone according to the social or professional setting. For instance, modal verbs like “might,” “could,” and “would” soften requests or suggestions, creating a more deferential tone, while “must” and “should” imply obligation or necessity, contributing to a more assertive style. "The selection of modal verbs in

English provides speakers with a nuanced range of options to adjust tone, facilitating polite, assertive, or tentative expressions depending on the context²². This adaptability reflects a stylistic norm in English that values flexibility, allowing speakers to tailor modality to suit varying levels of formality.

In contrast, Russian modality achieves tonal variation through the use of modal particles and specific modal constructions, which allow for subtle adjustments in emphasis and formality. Modal particles like “ведь” (after all), “же” (emphasis), and “ли” (whether) add shades of certainty, emphasis, or shared understanding, adapting statements to fit both informal and formal registers. In conversational contexts, these particles create an accessible, familiar tone, reinforcing cultural expectations around transparency and relational closeness. In more formal settings, Russian modal constructions convey authority or necessity directly, reflecting a stylistic preference for clear, unambiguous communication. "Russian modality, through its use of modal particles, provides an implicit approach to tonal adjustment, where the context and relationship between speakers influence modal choices"²³. This implicit quality in Russian modality suggests a stylistic norm where context plays a critical role, with modal particles serving as subtle cues that align the tone with social expectations.

In professional settings, such as academic or business exchanges, these stylistic differences in modality may affect how statements of certainty, authority, and obligation are perceived. English speakers often use modality in academic and legal contexts to introduce tentative findings or suggestions, maintaining an air of intellectual humility. This contrasts with Russian norms, where more assertive modality in formal contexts reflects confidence and clarity. For example, an English statement like “These findings might indicate...” may be interpreted by a Russian listener as lacking confidence, whereas a Russian equivalent would likely be more definitive. “These differences in expressing certainty and authority through modality can influence cross-cultural communication in professional contexts, where each party might misinterpret the other’s tone as either overly cautious or overly assertive”²⁴. Bilingual professionals can mitigate these misunderstandings by clarifying intent and recognizing the cultural underpinnings of each modality style.

Conclusion

In summary, awareness of the stylistic nuances in modality can enhance cross-cultural understanding and help bilingual communicators avoid potential misunderstandings. English speakers can approach Russian directness as a reflection of cultural norms that value clarity and sincerity, rather than interpreting it as impoliteness. Russian speakers, in turn, can view English indirectness as an expression of respect and personal autonomy. By acknowledging and adapting to

22 Palmer, F. R. *Mood and Modality*. Cambridge University Press.-2001 pp. 14-15

23 Griffiths, P. *Introduction to English Semantics and Pragmatics*. Edinburgh University Press.-2006 pp. 55-56

24 Ozyumenko, V. "Modality in English and Russian Legislative Discourse: A Comparative Study," *Respectus Philologicus*, Vol. 22.-2012- pp. 37-39

these stylistic differences, bilingual communication can become more nuanced, respectful, and culturally attuned. Cross-cultural communicators, including business professionals and diplomats, can benefit from these insights by adjusting their communication styles based on their audience's cultural preferences. English speakers working with Russian colleagues may adopt more direct language to build trust, while Russian speakers may use softened English expressions to show respect for personal space. These practical applications demonstrate how knowledge of stylistic modality enhances communication across languages, helping speakers and writers navigate cultural nuances with greater confidence and respect.

Reference:

1. Palmer, F. R Mood and Modality. Cambridge University Press.-2001 pp. 14-15
2. Griffiths, P. Introduction to English Semantics and Pragmatics. Edinburgh University Press.-2006 pp. 55-56
3. Ozyumenko,V. "Modality in English and Russian Legislative Discourse: A Comparative Study," Respectus Philologicus, Vol. 22.-2012- pp. 37-39